

ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE, AS A PREDICTOR OF SCHOOL CULTURE AND TEACHERS' WELL-BEING AT SECONDARY LEVEL

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Organizational justice, School culture, Workplace well-being, Secondary schools

Article History

Received: 05 December 2025

Accepted: 15 January 2026

Published: 30 January 202

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Abstract

The present study aimed to examine the organizational justice, as a predictor of school culture and teachers' workplace well-being at secondary level. A causal-comparative research design was used to conduct the study. Population of the study was comprised of all secondary school male and female teachers of Multan division. Multi-stage sampling technique was used to draw sample of present study. Sample of present study was (Male=640, Female=450)1090 teachers were selected proportionately which were the 30% of total population. Three instruments were used in present study. The results of the study clearly indicate that organizational justice and school culture have a significant impact on teachers' workplace well-being at the secondary school level. Findings confirmed strong and significant relationships among the variables. Organizational justice emerged as the significant predictor, as it not only promotes a positive and collaborative school culture but also strongly enhances teachers' workplace well-being. Although school culture also contributes positively to well-being, its effect is weaker compared to organizational justice, suggesting that fair treatment, transparent procedures, and respectful interactions are more influential in shaping teachers' work experiences. It is recommended that head teachers may actively promote organizational justice and positive school culture to enhance secondary school teachers' workplace well-being.

Introduction

Competition among organizations has intensified in recent years. Research in organizational behaviour identifies several factors that contribute to organizational success. Some scholars emphasize employees' physical health, motivation, commitment, and job satisfaction as key determinants of effectiveness. Other researchers argue that employees' moral and spiritual dimensions play a central role in achieving organizational success (Rajablou, Sepasi, & Nourbakhsh, 2014). Justice represents a fundamental human need within society. Some researchers regard fairness, equity, and justice as closely related concepts, while most studies in organizational contexts use the term

organizational justice to examine these issues. Research on organizational justice identifies multiple dimensions, with most scholars agreeing on three core forms, namely distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice. Perceptions of fairness enhance kindness, satisfaction, motivation, commitment, trust, mindfulness, and self-control among employees and reduce stress, conflict, confusion, and disorder in the workplace. Organizational justice therefore plays a critical role in individual performance and organizational success. Empirical findings also indicate that organizational justice relatively positively influences the state of employees and significantly

influences organizational outcomes (Tahseen & Akhtar, 2015).

Organizational justice therefore plays a critical role in individual performance and organizational success. Empirical findings also indicate that organizational justice relatively positively influences the state of employees and significantly influences organizational outcomes (Tahseen & Akhtar, 2015). Organizational justice refers to the degree to which organizations to ensure equitable and fair treatment amongst employees. Perceived injustice leads to a weaken signals of employees' self-confidence, self-esteem and morale in result of which, motivation declines, creativity, commitment and performance at work. The presence of organizational justice therefore is an important force in the development and success of an organization. It also strengthens employees' morale and commitment in respecting the goals of organization (Rajablou, Sepasi & Nourbakhsh, 2014).

Justice plays a central role in sustaining social harmony by enabling people with diverse characteristics to coexist peacefully (Greenberg, 2003). Scholars link justice to social order and emphasize its importance in resolving conflict, noting that maintaining order becomes difficult in the absence of justice (Bali, 2001). In the Dictionary of Educational Administration and Supervision, justice is defined as granting employees' rights in proportion to their contributions to the organization and applying sanctions for violations of organizational rules (Demirtaş & Güneş, 2002). The concept of organizational justice gained prominence and became widely used following Greenberg's work in 1987 (Altınkurt & Yılmaz, 2010).

Organizational justice describes how justice operates within workplaces and focuses on whether employees receive fair treatment and how such treatment influences work related outcomes (Moorman, 1991). It reflects employees' perceptions of fairness in their organization (Cohen-Charash & Spector, 2001). Justice is understood as actions or decisions that are considered morally right because of ethics, religion, fairness, equity or law (Pekurinen et al., 2017) and has been a major concern among both organizations and employees (Swalhi et al., 2017). Organizational justice is more specific and refers to employee's perception of fairness in

organizational practices and decisions (Asadullah et al., 2017). Theory of organization just is derived from equity theory (Adams, 1963, 1965). This theory states that the individual compares the ratio of their work inputs to those of those others, which affects their attitudes The extent of participation in the organization (Colquitt et al., 2001).

The human factor is the basis of organizational performance and success. Organizations depend upon dedicated workers who are motivated, well trained and educated Number of employees to work well. Accordingly, organizations are trying to improve the level of satisfaction, motivation, commitment, trust, kindness, mindfulness and self-control in employees through fair treatment, on-going professional development, and training opportunities (Geijsel, Slegers, Leithwood, & Jantzi, 2003). School Culture Organizational culture is the integration of organizational goals and activities with social values, as well as the systematic attitudes and behaviors which are common to members of the organization. A strong organization in terms of culture, shared by both management and employees in the form of common beliefs and values, plays a critical role in setting structures that underpin sustainable development (Cameron, 2012). Since the 1980s, the concept of school culture been used to capture the defined traits of the organizational culture in educational institutions (Walker-Wied, 2005). School culture is the ethos and social environment of schools including administrative and organizational structures and the ways these elements interact to support or limit the professional learning of teachers (Avalos 2011). School cultures that are effective in creating a way to promote. teacher learning - encourage teachers to look together at the practice, share experiences, and develop authentic materials in the classroom and new knowledge over sustained periods of time (Van Driel et al., 2012).

A particular application of organizational theory is school culture. Organizational culture is composed of shared values, underlying assumptions, and expectations that govern behavior in organizations (Schein 2004). Since organizations are made up of people who are formed by different social and cultural backgrounds, organizations have different cultures in different societies and organizations.

School culture is how members of a school perceive, think and feel of their own environment (Erickson, 1987). It works as a holistic power that affects all people in the school community. School culture has been defined as shared assumptions, norms, values, and cultural artefacts that give direction for everyday practices and determine the way school members are operating (Maslowski, 2001).

School culture is exhibited in rituals, traditions, stories, interpersonal relationships, and symbolic artefacts, such as language. It is closely associated with the sustainable development of school, the well-being of school members and the attainment of goals in education. Interactions between individuals and groups is a central dimension in the culture of school. Prosser (1999) makes the important point that school culture is inclusive of not only patterns of perception and behavior but also the web of relationships connecting them. Supportive school cultures motivate teachers to try new things in their classrooms and work with colleagues, which encourages innovation and better teaching and learning. School culture is widely accepted as a complex construct comprised of a number of interrelated dimensions (Kruse & Seashore Louise, 2009). A positive school culture is often associated with meaningful professional development and better student learning outcomes (Engels et al., 2008).

Workplace well-being has received more and more attention with the development of positive psychology: it focuses on optimal human functioning rather than only being focused on problems. Research on workplace wellbeing draws upon this perspective by considering both the decrease of negative conditions as well as the promotion of positive factors including healthy lifestyles. Stress is defined as being an interaction between individuals and their work environment that occurs when individuals perceive that they cannot cope up with the demands of the environment (Scott-Howman & Walls, 2003).

Employee wellbeing refers to positive feelings, mental satisfaction and perceptions of opportunities to develop abilities and assure self-esteem (Ryff, 2014).

Organizations expect high levels of performance from employees and lack of employee well-being leads to decrease productivity and poor quality performance. When organizations are actively supporting employee Stone says that "well-being, employees are more likely to perform effectively." Employee well-being is closely associated with workplace outcomes such as occupational accidents, absenteeism, levels of performance, turnover and profitability (Erdogan et al., 2012; Ali, et al., 2025). Research has consistently revealed that low levels of employee well-being have a negative effect on both employees and organizations, poor performance, increased absenteeism, decreased motivation, and less organisational loyalty (Holland et al., 2013).

Jena (2021) defined employee well-being as a state of physical and mental health that entails emotional reactions, satisfaction, and the evaluation of your entire life. Nikolajevaite and Sabaityte (2016) observed that a considerable amount of time is devoted to work in the life of an employee and therefore well-being at work is of utmost importance. Well-being is part of individual success and addresses societal outcomes by increasing competence, decreasing stress and boosting job satisfaction. Research suggests that employees who are characterized by higher levels of well-being at work show higher levels of creativity, productivity, job loyalty, trust, and quality of service (Dicke et al., 2020). Where organizations have in the past focused on engagement through extrinsic motivation, there is increasing evidence that workplace well-being provides a more wholesome approach to engagement in an organization by creating strengths and pride in work roles (Cooper & Dewe, 2008).

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

Research Objective

1. To find out significant correlation among organizational justice, school culture and workplace well-being at secondary school level.

Methodology

The present study aimed to examine the organizational justice, as a predictor of school culture and teachers' well-being at secondary level. Present study adopted quantitative approach. A causal-comparative research design was used to conduct the study. Population of the study was comprised of all secondary school male and female teachers of Multan division. Multi-stage sampling technique was used to draw sample of present study. At first stage Multan division was selected on convenient basis. Presently there are four districts under Multan division, Multan, Burewala, Khanewal, Lodhran and Vehari. At

second stage public school male and female teachers were selected as sample of present study. As, there were two strata in the population, therefore stratified sampling technique was used to draw sample of the study. At third stage (Male=640, Female=450)1090 teachers were selected proportionately which were the 30% of total population. Three instruments were used in present study. Pilot testing of the study conducted to ensure the validity and reliability of the instruments of the study. Data were collected by the researcher. Data were analysed by using appropriate statistical techniques. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse the data. Descriptive statistics included frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviation, whereas inferential statistics were linear regression, Pearson r, independent samples t-test and one-way ANOVA.

Results

Table 1

Correlation between Organizational Justice and School Culture at Secondary School Level

Variables	M	SD	r-value	Sig.
Organizational Justice	118.14	16.29	.669**	.000
School Culture	124.00	13.31		

Findings show that a significant positive strong correlation ($r=.669^{**}$) between organizational justice and school culture was examined at

secondary school level. It is concluded that “a high level of organizational justice leads a positive school culture at secondary school level”.

Table 2
Effect of Organizational Justice and School Culture at Secondary School Level

Model	Unstandardized Co-efficient	Standardized Co-efficient	β	T	p	df	F	R^2
	B	Std. Error β						
Constant	59.40	2.19	.67	29.71	.000	1088	883.10	.45
Organizational Justice	.54	.018						

Dependent Variable: School Culture

A linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the effect of organizational justice on school culture. As shown in Table 2 that organizational justice was a statistically significant predictor, explaining 45% of the variance in

school culture ($R^2 = .45, p \leq .05$). The results further indicated that organizational justice significantly predicted school culture ($\beta = .67$), and the overall regression model was statistically significant ($F = 883.10, p < .000$).

Table 3
Correlation between Organizational Justice and Workplace Wellbeing at Secondary School Level

Variables	M	SD	r-value	Sig.
Organizational Justice	118.15	16.29	.789**	.000
Wellbeing	110.11	15.42		

Findings show that a significant positive strong correlation ($r=.789^{**}$) between organizational justice and workplace well-being was examined at secondary school level. It is concluded that a “high

level of organizational justice leads a high level of teachers’ workplace well-being at secondary school level”.

Table 4
Effect of Organizational Justice and Workplace Well-being at Secondary School Level

Model	Unstandardized Co-efficient	Standardized Co-efficient	β	T	p	df	F	R^2
	B	Std. Error β						
Constant	21.96	2.104	.79	42.29	.000	1088	1788.80	.62
Organizational Justice	.746	.018						

Dependent Variable: Workplace Well-being

A linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the effect of organizational justice on workplace well-being. As shown in Table 4 that

organizational justice was a statistically significant predictor, explaining 62% of the variance in workplace well-being ($R^2 = .62, p \leq .05$). The

results further indicated that organizational justice significantly predicted workplace well-

being ($\beta = .79$), and the overall regression model was statistically significant ($F = 1788.8, p < .000$).

Table 5

Correlation between School Culture and Workplace Wellbeing at Secondary School Level

Variables	M	SD	r-value	Sig.
School Culture	124.00	13.31	.469**	.000
Workplace Well-being	110.11	15.42		

Findings show that a significant positive moderate correlation ($r = .469^{**}$) between school culture and workplace well-being was examined at secondary

school level. It is concluded that a “positive school culture leads a moderate level of teachers’ workplace well-being at secondary school level”.

Table 6

Effect of School Culture and Workplace Well-being at Secondary School Level

Model	Unstandardized Co-efficient	Standardized Co-efficient		t	p	df	F	R ²	
	B	Std. Error	β						
Constant	42.80	3.87		.46	17.49	.000	1088	306.11	.22
School Culture	.543	.031							

Dependent Variable: Workplace Well-being

A linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the effect of organizational justice on workplace well-being. As shown in Table 6 that organizational justice was a statistically significant predictor, explaining 62% of the variance in workplace well-being ($R^2 = .22, p \leq .05$). The results further indicated that organizational justice significantly predicted workplace well-being ($\beta = .79$), and the overall regression model was statistically significant ($F = 306.11, p < .000$).

influence was weaker than that of organizational justice, suggesting that fair treatment, clear procedures, and respectful behavior are more important in shaping teachers’ work experiences. A recent large study (2025) in primary and secondary schools found that organizational justice significantly influences teacher well-being, with teachers’ trust in leaders and perceptions of fairness mediating this effect. This shows organizational justice as a key predictor of positive workplace experiences for teachers. An international public health study reported that organizational justice significantly predicts teachers’ subjective well-being, likely by enhancing job satisfaction, reducing burnout, strengthening relationships, and fostering trust within the school environment. These studies collectively demonstrate that fair organizational practices and equitable treatment are strongly linked with teacher well-being outcomes, reinforcing the present finding that organizational justice was the most influential predictor of teachers’ workplace well-being. Large-sample evidence from more than 1,300 teachers showed that procedural justice predicts

Discussion

The present study aimed to examine the organizational justice, as a predictor of school culture and teachers’ well-being at secondary level. Results of the study clearly show that organizational justice and school culture play an important role in teachers’ workplace well-being at the secondary school level. Findings of the study revealed that organizational justice was found to be the most influential factor, as it not only supports a positive and cooperative school culture but also strongly improves teachers’ workplace well-being. Although school culture also had a positive effect on well-being, its

organizational citizenship behavior and that teacher burnout negatively impacts OCB. These behaviors reflect cooperative school culture and healthier teacher functioning. These findings provide support for the idea that organizational justice enhances cooperation, collaborative behaviors, and a positive overall school culture, which aligns with your finding that justice supports a cooperative culture. Teacher wellbeing remains conceptually fragmented, lacking a clear and universally accepted definition (Ozturk et al., 2025). Definitions range from the individualistic and fluid (McCallum & Price, 2016) to more structured, multidimensional models such as that of the OECD, which outlines cognitive, subjective, physical and mental, and social dimensions (Viac & Fraser, 2020). The issue of a clear definition is further complicated by the inconsistencies in the classification of constructs such as self-efficacy and resilience. These terms are often used variably as either components of wellbeing or as impacting factors (Viac & Fraser, 2020).

Recent studies have criticised deficit-based models and purely positive psychology approaches because they do not fully explain the complex and changing nature of teacher well-being (Hascher & Waber, 2021; Ozturk et al., 2024). A review of 61 studies by Ozturk et al. (2024) showed that most research has defined teacher well-being mainly in terms of professional or work-related factors. Only a few studies considered positive, negative, and professional aspects together. These findings highlight the need for broader definitions of teacher well-being that reflect teachers' real-life experiences and recognise well-being as a multidimensional concept.

Teaching involves continuous emotional, mental, and physical interaction with students, colleagues, school leaders, and the wider education system.

Conclusion

The present study aimed to examine the organizational justice, as a predictor of school culture and teachers' well-being at secondary level. Findings of the study concluded that there was significant strong positive correlation existed between organizational justice and school culture, whereas a significant moderate positive correlation was found between organizational justice and teachers' workplace well-being at

secondary level. Findings further revealed that school culture and teachers' workplace well-being has significant moderate positive correlation was found. Findings concluded that organizational justice is a significant predictor of school culture and teachers' workplace well-being at secondary school level.

Recommendations

Following recommendations were formed from the study.

1. Organizational justice was found a significant predictor of school culture and organizational justice at secondary school level, therefore it is recommended that the transparent policies for workload distribution, promotions, evaluations, and resource allocation might be clearly communicated and consistently applied in secondary schools.
2. Head teachers and school leadership teams may promote a positive school culture actively by boosting collaborative leadership, teacher collaboration, collegial support, shared goals, and professional learning communities.
3. Comparative studies across different regions, educational levels, and types of schools (public and private) are recommended to improve the generalizability of the findings.

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